

I want to develop a clear basis for implementing Success Management in (IT/IS) Projects

Reference: J. Varajão, Project Management Success Map / Success Canvas, v1 (2016) – v4 (2021), Department of Information Systems, University of Minho, 2021.

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Project Management Success Map[®] or Success Canvas[®]

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[HTTPS://WWW.SCIENCESPHERE.ORG/ISPMSIG/SUCCESSCANVAS](https://www.sciencesphere.org/ispmsig/successcanvas)

Project Management Success Map[®]

What is it?

The **Project Management Success Map[®]** (or just **Success Canvas[®]**) is a one-page overview that layouts what means “success” in your project and what is relevant to achieving it, highlighting success factors, expected benefits, and criteria for evaluating success. It is an excellent tool to create the basis for implementing *Success Management* in your projects.

Why should I do it?

It is helpful for both existing and new projects. The individual elements prompt thoughts within the different relevant aspects (e.g., success factors and criteria for evaluating success). At the same time, the capability to create a complete overview encourages perspectives and ideas about how those pieces fit together in the project. Its structure also helps focus the attention in each project’s time frame (before, during, and after the project).

? How can I use it?

To create a **Project Management Success Map[®]** or **Success Canvas[®]**, the easiest way is to organize activities around the following process.

(I.a) Project		(I.b) Participant(s)		(I.c) Date	
(II) What means "success" in your project?					

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(III) Objectives/Motivations (O)		(IV) Stakeholders (S)		(V) Deliverables (D)		(VI) Impacts/Outcomes/Benefits (I)		
What are the project's objectives/motivations?		Who are the project's stakeholders?		What are the project's deliverables?		What are the expected impacts/outcomes/benefits?		
ID	Objective/Motivation	Description	ID	Stakeholder	Description	ID	Impact/Outcome/Benefit	Description
O1			S1			D1	I1	
O2			S2			D2	I2	
O3			S3			D3	I3	
O4			S4			D4	I4	
O5			S5			D5	I5	
(VII) Criteria (C)		Time frames	e.g., EX ANTE (identify time frame)	1 - e.g., Project Planning (identify time frame)	2 - e.g., Project Executing (identify time frame)	3 - e.g., Project Closing (identify time frame)	e.g., EX POST (identify time frame)	
How success can be measured?			(III) Objectives/Motivations (O)					
ID	Criterion		Description	(IV) Stakeholders (S)				
C1				(V) Deliverables (D)				
C2				(VI) Impacts/Outcomes/Benefits (I)				
C3				(VII) Criteria (C)				
C4			(IX) Success Factors (F)					
C5								
(VIII) Dependencies (D)		(VIII) Dependencies (D)	(X) Ethical/Legal Concerns (E)	(XI) Barriers/Obstacles/Challenges (B)	Notes (N)			
There are any external dependencies?								
ID	Dependency	Description						
D1								
D2								
D3								
D4								
D5								
(IX) Success Factors (F)		(X) Ethical/Legal Concerns (E)		(XI) Barriers/Obstacles/Challenges (B)		Notes (N)		
What are the success factors?		There are any ethical or legal concerns?		There are any barriers (or risks) to success?		Observations		
ID	Factor	Description	ID	Concern	Description	ID	Note	
F1			E1			B1	N1	
F2			E2			B2	N2	
F3			E3			B3	N3	
F4			E4			B4	N4	
F5			E5			B5	N5	